

KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF NURSES TOWARD CARING OF ELDERLY PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background There are an estimated 605 million adults over the age of 60 in the world. In 2050, the world will have two billion older adults, with 80% of them living in developing nations. Elderly people may require long-term psychosocial treatment, nursing care, or hospitalization for a variety of health issues **Aim.** The aim of the study was to assess the Knowledge and Attitude of Nurses toward caring of Elderly Patients **Methodology.** A descriptive cross-sectional research study design was used. Study used purposive sampling technique. **Results.** The study reported that the knowledge participants with low knowledge were 68 (47.9%), The attitude of the participants with positive attitude were 90(63.4%). **Conclusion:** The study concluded that the majority of nurses having moderate knowledge, positive attitude towards caring of elderly patients.

INTRODUCTION

Old age is a period when social changes, irreversible physiological, spiritual and and losses of roles are experienced and the adaptation of the system to the environment decreases. Elderly individuals mostly experience more than one health problem and visit health institution usually(Argaw, Tamiru, Ayalew, & Habte, 2019).This domains continue till death after fourth decade.. During this time human being changes physically and physiologically.(Ali, Khan, Ali, & Bibi, 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) divides people over the age of 60 into three sub-periods: young-old (60-74 years old), old (75-90 years old), and oldest (more than 90 years old).(Sedri, Zakeri, Zare Zardiny, & Tavan, 2022). Around the world, there is a significant increase in the proportion and absolute number of elderly people.(Organization, 2015). Nurses play important role in the delivery of healthcare and the prevention

of diseases. They give medical services to numerous groups, including the disabled, ill, and elderly. As a result, they need to have the proper training for caring for adults who are senior. The provision of geriatric nursing care may be impacted by nurses' unfavorable attitudes towards patients and lack of expertise, according to research.(Ali et al., 2020). In order to provide comprehensive and high-quality treatment, nurses must be knowledgeable about geriatrics and have a favorable attitude towards them. In the medical field, a positive outlook always yields favorable results, and this is also true for the treatment of geriatric patients(Cheng et al., 2022) . Elderly patients often require specialized care, which can differ significantly from the care provided to younger patients. As a result, nurses who work with elderly patients need to have specific knowledge and skills to ensure that they can provide effective care.

In terms of knowledge, nurses need to have a good understanding of the physiological changes and health conditions that commonly affect the elderly, as well as the appropriate interventions and treatments for these conditions. and the potential side effects of medication commonly used by elderly patients. They also need to have knowledge of the social and psychological factors that can impact the health and wellbeing of the elderly, such as loneliness, isolation, and depression.

Nurses who work with elderly patients have a positive attitude towards caring for them. They see senior citizens as special people deserving of dignity, respect, and high-quality care. The chance to build relationships with their senior patients and their families is something that many nurses really cherish.(Dikken, 2017). However, Certain difficulties that nurses may have when providing care for elderly patients have also been brought to light by various research.

These challenges may include physical and cognitive limitations, communication barriers, and social isolation.(Ashiq & Asad, 2017).

METHODS

The cross sectional study design will be conducted to assess Knowledge and attitude of Nurses toward caring of Elderly people at tertiary care hospital. The purposive sampling techniques was used. The study population was staff nurses of surgical and medical wards of Jinnah hospital Lahore. The setting of the study was Jinnah hospital Lahore. The duration of this study was 9 months. The study sample was 142 calculated through slovin's formula. An adapted questionnaire of knowledge, attitude was used to gather the information from the study sample. All the student's nurses and internship nurses. Those nurses who are new in the job. Data was collected an adopted questionnaire of knowledge and attitude towards caring of elderly patient. After collecting data, the data was compute analyze by software program (SPSS) version (22). The ethical consideration was followed which is organize by the superior university department of nursing. The participant all the confidentiality was ensure any participant who are not willing to participate can be withdraw from the study at any time. There will be no potential harm and potential benefits for the study.

CHAPTER ANALYSIS

Variable	Category	Frequency%
Age	21-25 years	34 (23.9%)
	26-30 years	52 (36.6%)
	31-35 years	36 (26.1%)
	36-40 years	19 (13.4%)
Gender	Male	31(21.8%)
	Female	111 (78.2%)
Marital Status	Single	73 (51.4%)
	Married	69 (48.6%)
Experience	1-5 years	66 (46.5%)
	6-10 years	64 (45.1%)
	10-15 years	11 (7.7%)
	Above than 15 years	1 (.7%)
Qualification	Diploma in Nursing	38(26.8%)
	Post RN	64 (45.1%)
	BSN (Generic)	40 (28.2%)
Department	Medical wards	33(23.2%)
	Surgical wards	65 (45.8%)
	Others	44(24%)

Table no 1. Demographic characteristics

This demographic table shows that majority of age group with 26-30 years. Majority population were female. The Majority with single marital status. Majority of nurses with 1-5 years' experience. Majority with Post RN in Nursing. Majority of nurses working were in Surgical wards.

Table 2: Knowledge questionnaires

Majority of the Participants have poor knowledge regarding "Urinary incontinence in an older person may indicate that the person is suffering from UTI.". Majority of the Participants have poor knowledge regarding "Forgetfulness, concentration issues and

indecisiveness are parts of aging rather than indicators of depression.'. Majority of the Participants have good knowledge regarding "Patients with a cognitive disorder, such as dementia, are at increased risk for delirium. Majority of the Participants have good knowledge regarding "In general, older people are more sensitive to medication because their kidney and liver functions are declining". Majority of the Participants have poor knowledge regarding "Meeting with families during patient assessment is only required for persons suffering from dementia".

Questions	Respond	Frequency %
Urinary incontinence in an older person may indicate that the person is suffering from UTI.	True	30 (21.1%)
	False	112 (78.9%)
Forgetfulness, concentration issues and indecisiveness are parts of aging rather than indicators of depression	True	70(49.3%)
	False	72(50.7%)
Patients with a cognitive disorder, such as dementia, are at increased risk for delirium	True	111 (78.2%)
	False	31 (21.8%)
In general, older people are more sensitive to medication because their kidney and liver functions are declining	True	113(79.6%)
	False	29(20.4%)
Meeting with families during patient assessment is only required for persons suffering from dementia	True	36 (25.4%)
	False	106 (74.6%)

Table 3: Attitude questionnaires

Majority of the participants were positive attitude regarding "I feel good taking care of the Elderly". Majority of the participants were negative attitude regarding "I see the care of elderly is being

time consuming". Majority of the participants were positive attitude regarding "The older the elderly the more demanding he/she becomes".

Questions	Respond	Frequency%
I feel good taking care of the Elderly	Disagree	7 (4.9%)
	Agree	36 (25.4%)
	Neutral	10 (7.0%)
	Strongly agree	88 (62.0%)
	Strongly disagree	1(.7%)
I see the care of elderly is being time consuming	Strongly disagree	1 (.7%)
	Disagree	56 (39.4%)
	Neutral	19 (13.4%)
	Strongly agree	17(12.0%)
	Agree	49(34.5%)
The older the elderly the more demanding he/she becomes	Strongly agree	35(24.6%)
	Disagree	9(6.3%)

	Neutral	16(6.3)
	Agree	82 (57.7%)

DISCUSSION

Majority of Participants respond to false option to the question that the “Urinary incontinence in an older person may indicate that the person is suffering from UTI.” that were 112(78.9%). Majority of Participants respond to false option to the question that the Forgetfulness, concentration issues and indecisiveness are parts of aging rather than indicators of depression were 72(52.7%). Majority of Participants respond to true option to the question that Patients with a cognitive disorder, such as dementia, are at increased risk for delirium 111(78.2%). Majority of Participants respond to false option to the question In general, older people are more sensitive to medication because their kidney and liver functions are declining were 113(79.6%). Majority of Participants respond to false option to the question that Meeting with families during patient assessment is only required for persons suffering from dementia were 106(74.6.%). Majority of the nurses were strongly Agree 88(62%) to the question “I feel good taking care of the Elderly”. Majority of the nurses were Disagree 56(39.4%) to the question I see the care of elderly is being time consuming”. Majority of the nurses were agree were 82(57.7%), to the question “The older the elderly the more demanding he/she becomes”.

CONCLUSION

The current study concluded that the nurses have positive attitude but moderate knowledge about elderly care. Education and training programs aimed at enhancing nurses’ knowledge of elderly care and fostering a more compassionate attitude are recommended to ensure the highest quality of care for elderly patients.

LIMITATION

The current study used cross-sectional study design to identify the knowledge, attitude of nurses toward caring of elderly patients

RECOMENDATION

- The current study investigates the level of knowledge and attitude of nurses regarding care of

elderly patient. The future research can work on the enhancement of knowledge and attitude to conducted experimental study by which they can assess knowledge and attitude to give the intervention for enhancement of knowledge and attitude towards caring of elderly among nurses

- The future researchers can play a part to implement education programs and familiar about regarding the correct care of elderly through workshop, training programs, seminar lecture and research

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